

Simulation Explanation

The finite element simulation can be carried out in Solidworks2014 with the planar model, Part1-1.SLDPRT, and the 3D model, 3D-0mm.SLDPRT.

You can also simply use the data we've got in Matlab2014.

Files in the planar simulation

- Part1-1.SLDPRT
- GF1-Var1-K1.mat
- mysol.m
- Forc.m

Files in the 3D simulation

- 3D-0mm.SLDPRT
- GF_Var1_K1.mat
- mysol1.m
- Forc1.m

Operation in Matlab2014. Take the planar simulation as an example.

Double click the file, GF1-Var1-K1.mat to load the force, GF1, the variable, Var1, and the initial stiffness matrix, K1.

Open the file, mysol.m, then run it.

You can see three variables, SK, K0, and ans, in the command window.

SK is the force stiffness matrix calculated using the method proposed in this paper.

K0 is the force stiffness matrix calculated using the conventional method.

ans is the deviation matrix.

For the 3D simulation, the procedure is similar.

Double click the file, GF_Var1_K1.mat to load the force, GF, the variable, Var1, and the initial stiffness matrix, K1.

Open the file, mysol1.m, then run it.

You can see three variables, SK, K0, and ans, in the command window.

SK is the force stiffness matrix calculated using the method proposed in this paper.

K0 is the force stiffness matrix calculated using the conventional method.

ans is the deviation matrix.